

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC CULTURE IN THE PROCESS OF PROFESSIONAL TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF HISTORY

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Annotation

This article examines the importance of didactic culture in the process of professional training of future history teachers, as well as the need to revise and modernize didactic training in the framework of professional training of future history teachers.

Keywords: professional training, professional culture, didactic culture, complex formation, interactive character, didactic values, didactic training, self-reflection, introspection.

The modern geopolitical conditions of the development of society determine certain conditions for the professional training of future teachers of historical science, including the development of didactic culture. In the world, systematic work is being carried out to strengthen the emphasis on the study of history and, on this basis, to educate the younger generation and effectively implement the process of forming ideological immunity in them. In this regard, it is worth mentioning that the issues of methodological interpretation of the study of historical, spiritual, educational and pedagogical concepts and their implementation in the process of improving the educational system were outlined in UNESCO educational programs, UNESCO's concept of international education until 2030 and other similar programs. On this basis, systematic actions are being implemented to improve the effectiveness of the development of pedagogical skills, professional competence and didactic culture of teachers of history for the performance of these tasks.

In recent years, the discussion of the importance of teaching history in the Republic of Uzbekistan has aroused great interest in society, government, scientific and pedagogical community, since serious, fundamental changes are taking place in the social life of our country. The spiritual unity of the people and the moral values that unite us are important development factors, such as political and economic stability. When society only has a system of moral guidelines, the country is able to define and solve a wide range of national tasks while maintaining respect for its native language, its specific culture and cultural values, the memory of its ancestors and every stage of our national history. It is this national wealth that serves as the basis for the economic relations of life in

order to strengthen the unity of the country. In recent years, in connection with the development of a unified national idea of the state, as well as the need to maintain civic and ethnic identity in the conditions of a multi-ethnic society in compliance with tolerance standards, the tasks of the teacher of history, that is, the development of the worldview, thinking of educators, have significantly changed.

The concept of improving the educational system of the Republic of Uzbekistan (for the period up to 2030) sets the goal of education to “humanize socio-economic relations, become the most important factor in the formation of new life Relations of the individual.”

The scientific definition of the concept of “history” has two main meanings. The first is “history as the process of the progress of society”, the second is “history as the science that studies the progress of society”. That is, the object of Science and the science itself are defined by a single term, which requires that this case be taken into account when determining the content of the concept. Most historians believe that the development and transformation of society is the object of historical science. Given the multifaceted peculiarity of history as a science, it can be understood that its goals and objectives are of a multi-level nature:

the state level is the formation of a single concept of the civil and moral policy of the state in the upbringing of the younger generation;

the social level is the development of an adequate understanding of past, present and future relationships among all members of society through the analysis of historical relationships;

the individual level is the formation of the subjective ideas of the individual about historical reality, his connection with the past and its impact on the future, awareness of the history of the country and its place in the world of his generation.

The goals and objectives of these degrees must be achieved by studying “History” at the school. “History “is defined in the pedagogical encyclopedia as a general educational discipline” a teaching discipline that allows students to apply historical knowledge, skills and competencies in a variety of life situations.” In this case, “ history ” as a teaching science serves as a means of acquiring a high-level culture that respects the peculiarities of historical education, its development of civil and moral qualities of a person, the formation of a socially active member of society, including the laws and customs of society.

The study of history at the school is aimed at achieving the following goals:

- patriotic education (respect for the history and traditions of our homeland), respect for Human Rights and freedoms, democratic principles of the life of society;
- mastering the skills of working with various sources of historical information;
- formation of value orientations in the process of acquaintance with historically formed cultural, religious, ethno-national traditions;
- the application of knowledge and ideas about historically formed social norms and systems of values for life in a multicultural and multinational society, participation in intercultural interaction, tolerance attitude towards representatives of other peoples and countries.

It should be recognized that the main positive result of the reforms carried out in the educational range of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the creative freedom of the teacher, the possibility of choosing educational programs, textbooks and teaching technologies. However, it should be noted that, in addition to the advantages of the new situation, negative consequences have arisen, and most of the author's concepts and approaches implemented in history textbooks are perceived with difficulty by teachers and students as early as today. In a number of cases, the principle of integrity of historical education is violated. The abundance of authorial approaches does not guarantee the high quality of textbooks on its own. The problem of teaching history is due to the inability to realize the need to teach history at school. All modern history textbooks are accurate about history, do not provide knowledge, or there are reprints of old history textbooks adapted for politics. This is a paradoxical case in which history textbooks look the same, but due to its archaic nature, it does not correspond to the realities of the time and is not accepted by modern youth. At the same time, in the process of professional training of future teachers of history, these problems intensify and begin to acquire a personal character as well.

Today, the majority of teachers consider the main problem of teaching history at the school to be the problem of the intellectual and moral development of the personality of a teacher of history, the problem of methodological support for his activities as a teacher of history and the problem of stimulating students. We believe that these shortcomings and problems can be overcome in the future by developing such a concept as the "didactic culture of the history teacher", which defines historical education corresponding to the goals of the personality of society, teachers and students. It should be noted that

we are not considering didactic culture as a social experience of the development of didactic Sciences in general, but personal aspects in which the future science of history determines the professional activity of the teacher.

In our research on the professional training of the future history teacher, we can point out that didactic culture as an integrative peculiarity of the history teacher should include the following aspects:

- system of personal and professional values;
- a set of general cultural, general professional competencies with a didactic orientation;
- potential for self-development and self-control;
- implementation of pedagogical activity in accordance with didactic principles.

The didactic culture of the teacher of history science ensures the preservation of humanistic and cultural-historical values, contributes to the formation of a system of value orientations and historical knowledge of the student, as well as creative self-development.

The analysis of the gap in the development of didactic culture of future teachers of historical science indicates the need to revise and modernize didactic training within the framework of professional training of institutions of Higher Educations in the pedagogical direction. These changes should be aimed at developing the following aspects:

1. Understanding the principles of teaching history: Future History teachers should have a deep understanding of the principles of teaching history, including the importance of the active role of students in the educational process, the use of sources and methods of historical research, the analysis and interpretation of historical facts and events.

2. The use of modern pedagogical approaches and technologies: didactic exercises should ensure that future teachers of history are familiar with such modern pedagogical approaches as differentiated teaching, problem teaching, project activities and collective education. In addition, it is important to introduce students to the use of information and communication technologies in the teaching of history, including the use of computer programs, interactive whiteboards, online resources and multimedia materials.

3. Development of communication skills: teachers of history should have effective communication skills that allow them to build reliable relationships with their students, conduct dialogues and discussions, ask questions that they

can engage in activities and encourage critical thinking. Didactic training should include training and practical tasks aimed at developing these skills.

4. Adaptation to the individual needs of students: each student has its own needs, abilities and learning style. Future history teachers should be prepared to adapt the learning approach to meet these individual needs. Didactic classes should include differentiated teaching methods that allow teachers to adapt content, methods and assessments to each student's level and ability.

5. Development of reflexive practice: Future History teachers should critically reflexive their pedagogical practices, analyze their methods and approaches, and make the necessary adjustments. Didactic training should motivate students to self-reflexion, introspection(self-analysis) and continuous professional development.

In conclusion, it can be said that making changes to the didactic training of future teachers of historical science in institutions of higher educations in the pedagogical direction requires a systematic approach, including the analysis of existing programs, the development of new courses and modules, conducting practical classes, updating educational materials and organizing professional assistance and mentoring for students. These changes help train qualified history teachers who are able to conduct classes effectively, inspire students to study history, and develop their cognitive and critical skills.

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